

ZERO IMPACT DESIGN OF BUILDINGS. SUPPORTING DESIGN OF NZEB BY A DESIGN METHOD

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ABSTRACT

Economic and sustainability problems led to planned actions to reduce energy consumption of buildings and the related carbon dioxide emissions gradually to zero. However, very few designers have the necessary skills or experience to design net zero energy or net zero impact buildings. Therefore it was researched whether it is possible to support the design process for Zero Impact Buildings in by applying a design method. This method was tested in workshops with professionals. The research is done in close cooperation with the Dutch professional organizations of building design. As we want to prepare out student for their professional career the findings of the research were implemented and tested in our educational master program.

Keywords: Integral Design, Net Zero Energy Buildings, Morphological Overview.

INTRODUCTION

Strong fluctuating and rising energy prices, depletion of fossil fuel and growing awareness of global warming led to planned actions to reduce carbon dioxide emissions. In the Netherlands the stakeholders of the built environment agreed with the government to increase gradually to 0-energy new houses over 25% in 2012, and 50% in 2016. The UK adapted an even more ambitious policy where all houses should be CO₂ neutral by 2016.

This led to the development of Zero Emission Buildings: a building which emits virtually '0 (zero)' carbon dioxide (Kang et al, 2010). However this new target in building design ZEB, requires totally different approach from conventional building in terms of design, construction and operation (Ritter, 2010). That goal is very ambitious for the moment (Opstelten et al, 2007) and can only be realized by applying renewable energy source and an extreme low energy use of the building.

In order to achieve sustainable future the current design practice should be changed to adopt Zero Emission Building, and so should architects change their traditional role in the design process (Kang et al, 2010). The design process for a Zero Emission building is quite differently framed from a standard code compliant building and it is essential that an Integrated Design Process is used from the outset of the project to ensure success (AIA, 2009). A cost-effective Zero Emission Building is however a realistic possibility with an integrated design process (Torcellini et al, 2010).

Design education needs to help engineering students and architectural students to develop the necessary skills to successfully handle design tasks (Adems et al 2003) and so give them the knowledge and ability to realize this aim is the main intention of the multidisciplinary masters' project 'Integral design'. To test our ideas for a new educational approach experiments were done in a situation as close to design practice as possible: in workshops for professionals (Savanovic, 2009).

The constant and radical changes which characterizes modern world makes it (Williams et al, 2010), as Dineen and Collins (2005) observe, impossible: 'to base our future on the certainties of the past. Unable to define what we need to know, we have begun to focus on how we will need to know, on the flexibility and openness which characterizes creative thinking'. In design one has to work with ill-defined problems were the wanted solution and the problem itself develops almost in parallel at the early stages of the design process. Also the amount of relationships and dynamic social interactions makes it increasingly complex. Therefore a method is needed to structure this wicked problem (Simon, 1969).

METHODOLOGY

In the Netherlands such a model was developed: a prescriptive design model to teach design to mechanical engineering students at the University of

Twente (van den Kroonenberg, 1974). Called the methodical design model, it was based on the combination of the German and the Anglo-American design schools (Blessing 1994). When developing his design method van den Kroonenberg took only the most essential elements of the many different design methods that were proposed at that time. He focused on the need for a methodical ordering of the design activities in an overall design framework and looked at the difference between research and design in analogy with General System Theory (Zeiler 2007, Zeiler and Savanovic 2009).

To design is to formulate solutions, taking into account the targets to be achieved, the available resources and the prevailing constraints. In order to survey solutions, designers classify them based on various features. This classification provides means for decomposing complex design tasks into manageable size problems. An important decomposition is based on building component functions. The functional decomposition is carried out hierarchically so that the structure is partitioned into sets of functional subsystems and the decomposition is carried out until arrived at simple building components whose design is a relatively easy task.

Using the described function-oriented strategy, the integral design model allows various design complexity to be separately discussed and generated (sub) solutions to be transparently presented. Subsequently, the model makes it possible to link different abstraction levels with the phases in the design process, while maintaining a basic four-step design cycle (generate, synthesize, select, shape) recognizable within each phase. The functions required for working with the model can be regarded as what a design is supposed to fulfill: the intended behavior or intended characteristics of the object. The design process can be even more structured by giving an overview of the considered functions and aspects and their solution alternatives, this is called a morphological chart (Zwicky and Wilson, 1967). A distinguishing feature of Integral Design is the intensive use of morphological charts to support design activities in the design process and to visualize solution alternatives. Morphological charts were derived from the General Morphological analysis, based on the pioneer work by Fritz Zwicky (1948). General Morphological analysis was developed as a method for structuring and investigating the total set of relationships contained in multi-dimensional, non-quantifiable, problem

complexes, its history and some applications is given by Ritchey (2010). It was Norris (1963) who first introduced the application of the morphological approach into the domain of engineering design methods. The use of morphological charts also has definite advantages for communication and - notably - for group work (Ritchey, 2004).

The morphological chart is formed by decomposing the main goal of the design task into functions and aspects, which are listed on the first vertical column of the chart, with related subsolutions listed on corresponding rows. The functions and aspects are derived from the program of requirements.

INTEGRAL DESIGN

The in the Netherlands familiar model of Methodical Design (Blessing 1994) was extended into an integral design model by us by adding an evaluation step. So a distinctive feature of the integral design model is the four-step pattern of activities (generating, synthesizing, selecting and shaping, see Fig. 1), that occurs on each level of abstraction with the design process.

Figure 1. The four-step pattern of Integral Design

Another change to the original Methodical Design method was the extended use of morphological charts and the transformation of those into a morphological overview. The use of morphological charts within the Integral Design method supports step 1 and step 2 of the Integral design method's four step pattern, see Fig. 1.

The morphological charts made by each individual designer can be combined into a (team) morphological overview, see Fig. 2, after discussion on and the selection of functions and aspects considered important for the specific design. A morphological overview is thus generated by combining the different morphological charts made by each discipline after discussion on and the selection of functions and aspects of importance for the specific design, as well the relevant solutions to the agreed sub functions or aspects.

Figure 2. Building the morphological overview; Step 1: The Morphological overviews show the agreed functions and aspects (step 1) of the different morphological charts. Step 2: The Morphological Overview with the agreed on sub solutions (step 2) from the separate morphological charts.

EXPERIMENTS

In 2001 a research project started in the Dutch building industry using Integral Design methodology as a model for improving sustainable building design by structuring knowledge of building design team members. This approach was tested in several experiments (Zeiler et al, 2005).

WORKSHOPS INTEGRAL DESIGN FOR PROFESSIONALS

Since 2005 together with the Dutch Royal society of architects (BNA) and the Dutch Association of Consulting Engineers (NLIngenieurs), 5 series of workshops were organized. In total 107 experienced professionals voluntarily participated from these organizations. The average age of the participants was 42 and they had on average 12 years of professional experience. The participants of each discipline were randomly assigned to design teams, which ideally would consist of one architect, one building physics consultant, one building services consultant and one structural engineer. After each design session the participants present the results to each other and get feedback from the organizers. The participants are rearranged after each design session so that no one works together with someone else more than once, this to avoid a learning effect in the teams during the different design session. The workshops started with a lecture introducing Integral Design and are followed with other supportive lectures about sustainable energy systems, the use of morphological overviews and overall feedback of the results to all participants. The workshops typically include around twenty participants. Starting with a three day practice-like 'building team' concept, in which all disciplines are present within the design team from the start, the

integral design method workshops have evolved to finally a two-day series, see Fig. 3.

Figure 3. Professional organisations' Workshops series, four different design sessions

In the workshops stepwise changes to the traditional building design process, in which the architects starts the process and the other designer join in later in the process, are step wise introduced in the set up of the design sessions, see Fig. 3:

- (1) all disciplines start working simultaneously within a design team from the very beginning of the conceptual design phase,
- (2) the integral design method with its morphological charts and morphological overviews are applied.

The application of morphological overviews during the set up of the third design session demonstrates the effect of transparent structuring of design functions/aspects and generated (sub) solution proposals. Additionally, the third setting provides one full learning cycle regarding the use of morphological overviews.

During two days, in four different design sessions, the team had to perform a specific design task. The design tasks during these two days were on the same level of complexity;

1st design session: pavilion sustainable pavilion

In design session 1 each architect was given the task to design a 'parasite' structure to be placed on the building the workshop was taking place in. For full description of the design task (Savanovic 2009). Initially, in the first design session, which lasted approximately 30 minutes, the architect worked alone on the design. After the initial part of design session 1, the other team members met in the second part of the design session, to discuss the design and work together further on it.

2nd design session: net zero energy office

The task was to design a net zero energy office building. All participants started together at the same moment with the design process but in mono disciplinary groups. After this first part of the design session 2 the participants were divided into new multi disciplinary teams. In this session 2 all participants started together with the same information about the project in contrast with the 2nd part of design session 1.

3th design session: sustainable roof apartments

The task was to design net zero energy apartments on the top floor of the building. The participants were given an introduction on Integral Design and an explanation on how to use the tools of Integral Design, the morphological chart and the morphological overview. The design teams started as multidisciplinary teams working with the morphological charts and morphological overview. Design session 3 represented a learning-by-doing opportunity for the individual disciplines and the design teams. After the teams completed tasks set in session 3, time was given to feedback to the teams, to appraise the teams' work and to answer any questions that arose.

4th design session: net zero energy school

The task was to design a school with healthy and sustainable environment for children. The same location and overall demands as for net zero energy office design task was used. Design session 4 represents the very last stage in the cycle of research in this research project. By using all interventions as part of the Integral design method, the effect of its application could be determined.

MULTIDISCIPLINARY MASTER DESIGN PROJECT FOR SUSTAINABLE CLIMATIC DESIGN 2005 - 2010

In connection with the Integral design research project for professional in the Dutch building industry, the Department of Architecture, Building and Planning of the University of Technology Eindhoven developed an educational project, the Multidisciplinary master design project. Interaction between practice, research and education forms the core of the 'integral approach'. Therefore the concept of the integral design workshop for professionals was implemented within the start-up workshop of our multidisciplinary masters' project. The basis of this project, which serves as a learning-by-doing start-up workshop for master students, is the Integral design method with its use of morphological overviews. The different design assignment all were related to the design of zero energy buildings. Such complex task requires early collaboration of all design disciplines involved in the conceptual building design.

Students from architecture, building physics, building services, building technology and structural engineering were offered the opportunity to participate. In the workshops an average 22 students participated each year, average age 23 and which had no design experience from practice. The procedure was the same for the professional workshops; the only criterion for participation was being a master student.

The students were assigned to design teams of different disciplines in such a way as to have all disciplines represented in each team. The students are intensively guided by staff from each discipline involved and the meetings with the individual staff members are according to a strict scheme. After the sessions with the students, the staff reflects the meetings together. The whole project took one semester.

MULTIDISCIPLINARY MASTER DESIGN PROJECT FOR SUSTAINABLE CLIMATIC DESIGN WITH PROFESSIONAL PARTICIPATION 2011

Based on the multidisciplinary master design project workshops, a more compact version of the workshops was developed and introduced in the Master project Integral design 2011. Instead of 4 design session within two whole days, the workshops were reduced to one afternoon session on the first day and one morning session on the second day. During the sessions 1 and 2, 29 students participated and in session 3 and 4, 27 students participated (5 Building Services, 6 Structural Design, 3 Building Physics and

13 Architects). The average age of the students was 23 and they had no professional experience. In session 3 and 4 six professionals participated, in each student design team one, which were on average 50 years old and had around 25 years experience. The teams existed out of different disciplines and were changed after each session. On day 1 the students had to perform the design task 1 of the former workshops in teams of two and design task 2 of the former workshops series in team of 4 students. After this, during the morning of the second day, they had to perform design task 3 together with one professional expert in each group. The workshops started with an afternoon setting consisting of two sessions and followed the next

morning by another two sessions. The focus of the workshops was to learn the students the use of morphological charts and morphological overviews. This was done by giving starting with a lecture about the Integral Design method and its specific application of morphological charts and morphological overviews as design tools.

The students were divided in design teams that during session 1, 2 and 3 all students worked only once with the same students. This to avoid a learning effect in teams as they otherwise starting to know each other better.

In session 1, 2 and 3 the participants started individual working on the different design task and making their own morphological chart, see Fig.4.

Figure 4. Workshops MIO project, four different set ups with different team configurations

1st design setting, 'parasite' design task

In design setting the teams were given the same design task as used in the Integral design research: to design a 'parasite' structure to be placed on the building that the workshop was taking place in. For full description of the design task see Savanovic [2009]. The 2 designers had to make their individual morphological chart and then combine them to a morphological overview.

2nd design setting, 'zero energy office'

The 2nd design task was to present a conceptual design for a net zero energy office and as such was also like assignment 1, the same assignment as used earlier in the Integral design workshops for professionals. All participants were divided into groups of 4, two architects and two engineers, and started individual at the same moment by making their individual morphological charts. After this first part of the design session 2 team's discussion ensued. The focus of this discussion was on fitting

the individual morphological charts into a team's morphological overview.

3th design setting, students with expert for a Net Zero Energy apartment building

The task was to propose a conceptual design for a 60 stories net zero energy (NZE) apartment building on a specific location. The design teams were formed based on the actual teams of the Master project Integral design (MIO-project). Besides 2 or 3 engineering design disciplines present in the design teams they had 2 or 3 architectural students. This meant that 5 or 6 students formed a design team. In addition each student team was strengthened by a professional expert. The members of the design teams started individual, making the morphological charts and after that worked together to make the morphological overview. After this first part of each session the teams put together the morphological charts to make a morphological overview as a team.

The individual part of the sessions 1,2 and 3 took 20 minutes and the team part lasted 40 minutes. In the first individual part of the sessions there was no communication between the participants. In session 1 the teams existed of an architectural student and an engineering student, all together 15 teams. In session 2 the teams existed of two architectural students and two engineering students, in this way there were formed 8 teams. In session 3 the students were again rearranged now in teams of 5 or 6 students. In addition each student design team was strengthened by an expert who joined the design team.

RESULTS

WORKSHOPS FOR PROFESSIONALS

The comparison of design setting 1 and 2 presents the effect of introducing all the different designers from the start without using support. This led to a decrease of the number of aspects and subsolutions, indicating a less effective design process. From the analysis of the workshops it could be concluded that the solution space, resulting from the number of functions and aspects considered, was significantly increased by applying the Morphological Overviews. A good example of this increase can be seen from the results from session 1 (without morphological charts and morphological overview) compared with the results of session 4 (with use of morphological charts and morphological overview), see Fig. 5.

Figure 5. Comparison of the number of aspects/functions and partial solutions being generated by the design teams in design session 1, 2 & 4.

It shows that more aspects and sub solutions were generated in setting 4 than in the previous settings 1 and 2. Besides the increase of the number of considered functions and aspects there is also a larger number of partial solutions for Net Zero Energy Buildings in session 4 compared to sessions 1 and 2, see Fig. 5.

MULTIDISCIPLINARY MASTER DESIGN PROJECT FOR SUSTAINABLE CLIMATIC DESIGN 2005-2010

Education should prepare students to become professionals therefore it is of importance to look into the appreciation of the proposed design tool within building design practice. The professional workshop formula was used to start the students' master project integral design team work. The results of the workshops in their final form held for professionals and students were compared and showed that the professionals were more positive about the workshops than the students (Zeiler et al 2009). The results of the workshops in their final form held for professionals and students are here compared. In these two workshops series 38 professionals participated, average age 42 and on average 12 years of design practice experience. In the two parallel workshops for students, 42 participated, average age 23 and with no design experience. Direct at the end of the workshops the participants were asked to fill in a questionnaire about the use of morphological overviews during the design sessions and about the concept of the workshops themselves, see Fig. 6. The responds of the professionals was 95% and that of the students was 76%.

Figure 6. Comparison results questionnaires the two last series workshop of two days for professionals and students, rating on a scale from 1-5.

The results of the questionnaires indicate that the participants thought the use of morphological overviews increases the insight in other disciplines, helps the communication and increases the number of relevant alternatives within the design process. The appreciations of professionals are on all aspects higher than that of the students.

MULTIDISCIPLINARY MASTER DESIGN PROJECT FOR SUSTAINABLE CLIMATIC DESIGN WITH PROFESSIONAL PARTICIPATION 2011

In the 2011 version of the Multidisciplinary master design project, students performed different design assignments in sessions 1, 2 and 3. In session 3 the student design teams were joined by a professional. After session 3, all participants were asked to fill in a questionnaire, which made it possible to compare the outcome of students as well as of professionals, see Fig. 7. Remarkable is that the professionals are the most positive group on whether they think the approach appropriate, as well as for the relevance of the approach.

Figure 7. Results comparison results questionnaires 2011, professionals - students, on a scale from (1-5)

The number of functions and sub solutions mentioned by the designers in their morphological charts were counted and are represented in Fig. 8. The same was done for the sub solutions mentioned by the design teams in their morphological overviews, see Fig. 8.

MC=Morphological chart, MO=Morphological Overview, Stu=students, Pro=Professionals

Figure 8. The average number of functions and part solutions mentioned in the morphological charts and morphological overview of the design session 1, 2 and 3.

This makes it possible to compare the results between the average number of functions and

subsolutions mentioned in morphological charts and morphological overviews for all three different design sessions. Although the design tasks were different for all three sessions they were seen as a stable factor, since from former research it was found that the complexity of these design task were quite similar and no significant effect on the results as such (Savanovic, 2009).

The teams formations for the different assignments were changed from teams of two (session 1) to teams of four (session 2) and teams of five or six (session 3). Fig. 8 shows that there is no significant difference in the average outcome of the morphological charts between the different sessions of the workshops. In all sessions combining morphological charts into a morphological overview leads to an on average increase of the number of functions and solutions as mentioned by the design teams.

Overall there is an increase of the number of solutions mentioned in the morphological overview after session one compared to session two (on average 24.5 compared to 27.3), which could be an indication that the students learned to improve the process of combining the individual morphological charts into the team's morphological overview. There is only a rather small difference between the students making the morphological charts in session 3 (MC3Stu) compared to that by the professionals (MC3Pro). Quite remarkable is also the small effect of adding a professional to the students teams in session 3, MO3 (7,8 functions and 30 solutions), compared to the outcome of session 2, MO2 (7,1 functions and 27,3 solutions). Overall the professionals generate more functions and aspects (on average 7) as compared to students (on average 5.6) but generate less sub solutions.

DISCUSSION

Sustainable building designs need to provide solutions for sustainability issues ranging from flexible use to renewable energy, energy reduction measures while maintaining and even increasing comfort level of the users.

New approaches are needed to bridge the gap between the worlds of theory and practice in building industry which look at designing as a process in which the concepts of function, behavior and shape of artifacts play a central role (Vermaas & Dorst 2007). Such integral design approach can eventually lead to an integral process, team and method - all the required conditions for innovation of the end product; the building (Seppänen et al 2007). The primary goal of this research was to find a way

to integrate architecture with different engineering disciplines into an integral design process for Net Zero Energy Building design. Right at the beginning of such integral building design project, a design method was offered to integrate in a meaningful way engineering knowledge and experience. The results show that the Integral Design-method is relevant for increased insight between design team members, which makes it easier to create Net Zero Energy Building-concepts. Applying the Integral Design method lead to an increase of the number of functions and aspects thought of as well as to an increase of the number of generated subsolutions which in result stimulates the creation of new concepts to achieve Net Zero Energy Buildings. From the analysis of the workshops it could be concluded that, the number of functions and aspects considered, as well as the number of subsolutions offered, was significantly increased by applying the Integral design method with its use of Morphological Overview. A good example of this increase can be seen from the results from session 1 (without morphological charts and morphological overview) compared with the results of session 4 (with use of morphological charts and morphological overview), see Fig. 5.

The comparison of design setting 1 and 2 presents the effect of introducing all the different designers from the start without using support. This led to a decrease of the number of aspects and subsolutions, indicating a less effective design process. This is inline with literature about brainstorm experiments (Nijstad et al 2003), where they also found out that by just bringing together more designers the productivity doesnot increase compared with the results from individual sessions. The team has to have a kind of guidance, in our case the Integral design method.

The results of the questionnaires, see Fig.6, indicate that the appreciations of professionals are on all aspects higher than that of the students. There were key differences between the results of students and professionals. The work of the design teams was also photographed, in 10 minute intervals. It is interesting to note the average development of the number of generated alternatives by the professional and by the student design teams. There is no big difference in the amount of aspects, but the number of proposed alternatives, student teams on average almost three times more sub solutions than the professional teams, and the process order in which the teams generate them is completely different (Savanovic 2009). Generally speaking the professional design teams tended to define the

aspects first and then produce relevant alternatives based on their experience. The student design teams generated the sub solution proposals and the functions/aspects more in parallel. However, they continued generating new proposals even till the last moments of the workshops. It appeared that they often did not know what to do with the produced (sub) solutions. The experience of the professional designers seemed to give them some advantage regarding making combinations of sub solutions to design concept structures, the integration of knowledge to solutions. These results indicated that students apparently have difficulties making the integration step. This could be the reason that the evaluation by the students is lower than that of the professionals, they do not experience the added value of the application of morphological overviews related to the integration step.

It needs to be stressed that the quality of the generated alternatives/proposals was not assessed. The purpose was to research if the use of the morphological charts would lead to a widening of the field of possibilities, which did seem to be the case.

Replacing an individual designer, architect, by a design team at the beginning of a design process, improves integration through concentration on most relevant aspects of the design task at hand (Zeiler et al, 2009). The relevancy of sustainable aspects is subjectively decided by design teams themselves, by continuously (re)interpreting design brief and design proposals. The necessary objectivity / transparency for other stakeholders is reached in presentation of the team interpretations of the design brief in the list of functions to fulfill and aspects to be met. Using the morphological chart helps to explain their interconnection.

It is questioned whether this way of working changes the architect's 'role' as different procurement routes (e.g. in UK) engage services at different stages. Some architectural practices in UK approach conceptual design stages and user engagement exercise jointly with a building services engineer to engage the users in design exercises selecting types of sedum roof, heating systems etc. without considering this a new 'method' or 'role' for the architect or engineer. However that way of working is still based on the traditional leading role of the architect in the conceptual design phase, where the architects ask for specific product related realization knowledge in connection to the architectural conceptual design. For example the sedum roof or heating system are in this case considered as add on's to the architectural design.

There is no real synergy within such a conceptual design phase. In such situations already most decisions are already implicitly made by the architect without the actual needed knowledge for them.

Professional workshops were organized for research into a new design education concept for architectural and engineering master students. This led to concept for student workshops as the starting point of a multi-disciplinary master design project for Net Zero Energy Buildings. Traditionally a design method is developed at a university where it is tested on students and then implemented in practice. In this research that was changed; the testing was done as near to practice as possible with professionals and then implemented at the university. The result was that, were normally the evaluation of the design method and its tools by practitioners lead to a lower appreciation than that by students; in this case the situation was reverse. The practitioners thought the design method and its tool of more value than the students.

When the new compact approach for the Integral workshop 2011 is compared with the results of the full two day workshop of 2010, there is only a slight decrease of the evaluation results, see Fig. 9. It was therefore decided that the new concept of the workshops should be preferred in future.

Figure 9. Results of questionnaires full two day workshop 2010 with new reduced workshop 2011, on a scale (1-5)

CONCLUSION

In near future Net Zero Energy/ Emission Buildings must be designed: buildings that over a period of a year on average generate as much energy as they use (Kilkis et al 2010). This is difficult as designers have to meet these new demands from society. New approaches in architectural design are needed to support especially the conceptual building design process. Integral design method, with its morphological overviews, could be used as a design support tool within Net Zero Energy Building design. By

structuring design (activities) and communication between design team members, morphological overviews can support reflection on the design results by the design team members themselves and in discussion with external stakeholders. The design process can be made transparent by the application of the integral design method. This makes it easier to build a bridge between architecture and engineering and to reach synergy between the disciplines. Within building design morphological overviews stimulate the emerge of new design concepts. The ratings of the evaluation questionnaires, by the participants of both the student workshops and the professional workshops, showed good results. Besides this the Integral Design workshops have become part of the permanent professional educational program of BNA (Royal Institute of Dutch Architects) since 2007. One of the participating architects of the workshops, Carl-Peter Goossen, became so enthusiastic about the design approach that he made it its leading principle in the design management of the projects of his company BouwQuest (Goossen, 2010a). A good example of his work is the Veldhuizen school in Ede. It will be the first new passive house primary school in the Netherlands. The construction of the school was finished in July 2011. The school has a green sedum roof and is a pilot project for an integral BIM approach (Goossen 2010b, AgenschapNL 2011), see Fig. 10.

Figure 10. The Veldhuizen school in Ede and its ventilation/conditionings system

An additional 'proof' for success is the fact that at the moment a course is being developed on Integral design for the Dutch society of building services engineers as part of their professional educational program which will start at the end of this year.

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